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Future Circular Collider

REPORT

RENEWABLE ENERGY SUPPLY FEASIBILITY ANALYSIS

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Disclaimer:

This document presents a summary of a feasibility analysis to supply the FCC with electricity from renewable energy sources, carried out by two consultancy companies (Accenture, McKinsey) who are active in this business and who regularly advise public and private organisations as well as governments for this subject matter. The analysis presents forward looking opportunities based on assumptions and market analysis supplied by the consultancy companies. The report does not imply that the research infrastructure will eventually be able to obtain the presented products and conditions. This depends on diligent business planning and contractual negotiations to be carried out by experienced experts in the domain, an in-depth knowledge of the market and a set of key players as well as strong policy support for a project of national and international interest. The consultants provide no warranties and are not liable for the correctness and completeness of the information.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations:

ARENH	Accès Régulé à l'Électricité Nucléaire Historique
CUF	Capacity Utility Factor
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
FCC	Future Circular Collider
FID	Financial Investment Decision
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
ISO	International Standardisation Organisation
ISP	Internet Service Provider
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Electricity
LHC	Large Hadron Collider
PPA	Power Purchasing Agreement
RES	Renewable Energy Source
ESG	Environmental, Social and Governance

1. SUMMARY

The FCC study commissioned a feasibility analysis for the supply with electricity from renewable sources to two companies who regularly carry out such investigations, McKinsey¹ and Accenture². This report summarises the results of this analysis and provides details about the assumptions, the supply scenarios, and the options to supply an FCC with renewable energy over a long time scale. The main findings are:

1. The FCC and the CERN **can be supplied with renewable energy sources (RES) during construction and operation phases at stable cost. The RES coverage goals impact the cost target.**
2. **France is an advantageous location** in the world and in Europe to provide an FCC with electricity from renewable sources at competitive cost.
3. **Supply of electricity from renewable energy sources will be competitive on a long-term time horizon** with respect to conventional energy sources, including de-carbonised nuclear energy and hydrogen fired gas turbines.
4. **Multiple incremental long-term Power Purchasing Agreements (PPAs)** are required for RES supply with multi-year durations that would be staged in time. None of the scenarios to obtain electricity from renewable energy sources requires venture capital contributions from CERN.
5. **The planning, implementation and operation of RES PPAs requires either the creation of a team staffed with experienced senior power purchasing experts or an outsourcing of the task** to a broker company. The first option can be more cost effective than the second option. An opportunity and cost comparison would need to be carried out to determine the most suitable scenario for managing a portfolio of PPAs.
6. **Obtaining adequate RES coverage takes several years.** Obtaining electricity at FCC operation scale from dedicated renewable energy sources such as offshore wind and PV plants via pre-FID PPAs requires about ten years.
7. **Offshore wind is the most suitable energy source for FCC.** To increase the RES coverage and to improve cost competitiveness and cost stability, at long term, a **combination of offshore wind, onshore wind and solar power is the most recommended RES technology mix.** Considering the already ongoing technological progress over the next fifteen years, this scenario should be complemented with battery storage (onsite or offsite energy storage PPA) to further decrease cost and carbon footprint. Energy storage is considered a key component to achieve good RES supply coverage.
8. **Providing the FCC with RES is an incentive for an accelerated energy transition.** It will not jeopardize the stability and availability of electrical energy in France and in Europe. Each renewable PPA to supply CERN with electricity will create jobs, build up additional RES capacities and improve the stability of the grid connections. The rationale for this development is that institutional partners are considered highly reliable customers and thus permit energy suppliers and network operators to integrate the cashflow in long-term development projects with stable and forecastable margins that in turn are guarantees for their investors who seek long-term fixed returns.

¹ Sophie Auchapt, & Joscha Schabram. (2023). Future Circular Collider: Clean Energy Supply Study (6.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7781077>

² Herschke, Philippe. (2023). Sustainable Energy Supply Concept for a Future Circular Collider (1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7781414>, restricted access.

9. **Purchasing electricity from RES in a future more open European electricity market can lead to lower prizes.** However, today the physical line and line allocation capacities between European countries are severely limited. At European level, CERN and the FCC are not considered to have a significant market impact. However, **seeking policy support at French national level for a project of national interest** to develop additional RES capacities pre-FID for the benefit of the research infrastructure and other customers is considered a possible lever arm by the consultants.
10. Including in a PPA selling of excess energy to the market, buying missing coverage and storing energy can be used to further optimise the cost and renewable energy coverage. This would also lead to the creation of societal impact by supplying electricity from renewable sources to the market.
11. **The preference for particle collider operation in particular seasons during the year needs still to be assessed in combination with additional socio-economic impact pathways** such as the recovery and supply of waste heat, the consumption of cooling water and the technical capability to dynamically adapt the load needs (e.g. standby mode, quicker than today cryogenics operation changes, operation with different energies and luminosities). From the renewable energy production perspective and the electricity price alone, the analysis so far did not reveal a preference for setting the collider operation to the winter or to the summer season (wind power production is higher between October and March than between April and September. However, this is also the period where demand and thus cost is higher³).
12. **The time to obtain a long-term RES PPA at competitive conditions is long (more than 2 years for general service coverage and about 10 years for FCC-scale dedicated resources).** The consultants identified about fifteen interested energy suppliers in France that can be approached to develop non-binding scenarios for the establishment of a suitable future energy mix that corresponds to FCC needs on a long-term time horizon. Such type of exploratory investigation can permit energy developers to approach the government to identify possibilities for building up new offshore wind and to make pledges for investors. Availability of suitable sites, zoning restrictions and authorization processes are the limiting factors to obtain RES within acceptable time frames. Engaging with an energy supplier pre-FID assures highly competitive prizes over sustained periods of time.
13. **The lifecycle greenhouse gas footprint for electricity from renewable energy sources will continue to drop.** A conservative estimate based on today's indicators for different electricity sources provided by the French agency for the ecological transition (Ademe) with an 80% RES coverage leads to an annual footprint of 40 000 to 55 000 t CO₂e for the FCC per year. This translates to 3 t CO₂e per researcher involved in the programme. It can be for example compared to the footprint of 5 t CO₂e per researcher and year in astronomy⁴. Per taxpayer funding the FCC programme, the footprint is less than 80 g CO₂e per year, 45 g with more than 80% RES coverage. 45 g CO₂e correspond to 20 to 30 minutes use of social media per person per year⁵, 5 to 8 emails with attachments⁶ or boiling 2 to 3 kettles of water⁷.

³ For seasonal electricity generation from renewable energy sources and electricity demand, see <https://ember-climate.org/insights/research/european-electricity-review-2023/>

⁴ <https://physicsworld.com/a/the-huge-carbon-footprint-of-large-scale-computing/>

⁵ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1177323/social-media-apps-energy-consumption-milliampere-hour-france/>

⁶ <https://www.cleanfox.io/blog/carbon-impact/digital-pollution-emails-and-carbon-emissions/>

⁷ <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/14/4/2195>

2. POWER PURCHASING AGREEMENTS

2.1. INTRODUCTION

A PPA is a typically long-term agreement to purchase energy at a predetermined price between a renewable energy source developer and a consumer — generally an organisation requiring significant amounts of electricity — or between a developer and a supplier who then resells the energy. The signing of a PPA can be understood as the sale of a project and its environmental attributes ("guarantees of origin"): it is a commitment that allows a renewable developer to make a financial investment decision (FID) using the criteria of profitability versus risk and/or achieve the funding necessary to execute the project.

Not all PPA types presented here are today available in France due to current national regulatory restrictions⁸. So far, the following types are known⁹: direct (or physical) PPA, sleeved (or indirect) PPA and financial (synthetic or virtual) PPA. The current situation does not exclude that with the evolution of the RES landscape and the ongoing deregulation further PPA types become available. For instance, "hybrid PPAs" including energy storage appear currently on the international and national markets.

Recently, an electricity market deregulation process has been engaged in France that will continue with the build-up of more renewable energy sources and the development of European energy cohesion policies. Electricity developers can also be suppliers if they are able to provide evidence for a certain capacity to RTE, the French national grid operator. Smaller developers supply their energy to a so called "electricity aggregator" who creates a virtual power plant that in turn assures the capacity required by their customers and the grid equilibrium responsibility required by RTE. Developers with capacities below 1 MW are legally required to supply via aggregators. Developers with individual capacities above 100 MW typically appear also as suppliers.

Today, more than 20 direct energy suppliers exist in France: EDF, Engie, TotalEnergies, Iberdrola, Méga Energie, Planète Oui, EkWateur, Ilek, Enercoop, Happ-e by Engie, Plü Energie, Mint Energie, Greenyellow, Energies du Santerre, Butagaz, Sowe, Elecocité, Wekiwi, Cdiscount Energie, Gaz Electricité de Grenoble, ENI and Vattenfall.

In addition, more than 200 organisations have obtained from RTE the certification to assure an equilibrium between energy production and consumption, becoming a so called "responsable d'équilibre"¹⁰, being able to aggregate energy sources and supply that energy. More than 70 of them have signed a contract to supply the energy via the national electricity grid with Enedis¹¹, one of the national energy distribution organisations. It should be noted that these organisations are not all located in France, opening in principle the possibility to obtain energy from other countries, although today transnational line capacities are limited. Some arbitrary selected examples of national suppliers include Alpiq, Alterna, Axpo, BKW, BCM, Bohr, BP, Centrica Energy Trading, COMAX, Compagnie National du Rhône, Dalkia, Danske Commodities, EDF, ekWateur, Elecocite, Enercoop, Engie, ENI, Eqinov, Exeltium, Flash, HEX, Hydronext, Iberdrola, Ilek, Mint, Next, NLG, Novajoule, Ohm, Primeo, Repower, RWE, Shell Energy, Seolis, Shell, Solvay, Statkraft, TotalEnergies, Uniper, Vattenfall, Voltalis.

⁸ The World Bank, "French standard power purchase agreements", 2021, online at <https://ppp.worldbank.org/public-private-partnership/library/french-standard-power-purchase-agreements>

⁹ DLA Piper, "France, Corporate Power Purchase Agreements", 8 June 2022, online at <https://www.dlapiperintelligence.com/corporateppa>

¹⁰ <https://www.services-rte.com/fr/decouvrez-nos-offres-de-services/devenir-responsable-dequilibre.html>

¹¹ It should be noted that for an FCC class facility electricity is typically obtained during the construction phase from distributors like Enedis, but during the operation phase a direct access to the grid via RTE is envisaged.

2.2. POWER PURCHASING AGREEMENT TYPES

This section provides a high-level general overview of different Power Purchasing Agreement (PPA) types. There are **two main PPA types** depending on where the energy is generated:

An **On-site ("private wire") PPA** is a contract for the supply of electricity from an ad hoc plant (e.g. photovoltaic) **located on the customer's property** and connected to its internal network. The renewable developer makes the investment and designs, installs, operates and maintains the plant. The energy generated by the solar panels is energy that the customer is no longer demanding from the grid, so the developer offers the customer this energy at a more competitive price.

An **Off-site PPA** is a contract associated with a **utility-scale plant** (e.g. wind farm or photovoltaic) **connected to the transmission or distribution network** of the country's electricity system to take energy from its point of origin to the consumption point. Off-site PPAs are further distinguished:

Off-site PPAs depending on the delivery point:

- **Physical PPA**
The developer sells the renewable energy to an end consumer either directly or through an energy retailer, which supplies the energy from the renewable asset. Missing energy is supplied from the retailer's generation portfolio. At the end of the month, the consumer receives a single bill for all its consumption, whether from the dedicated renewable installation under the PPA or other resources of the developer under the PPA or at the spot price.
- **Virtual PPA (sometimes referred to as financial or synthetic PPA)**
This is a financial instrument. No electricity flows from the producer to the consumer. The consumer deals directly with a renewable developer to agree the price of the energy (first contract). In addition, the consumer needs to buy electricity directly from an energy retailer (second contract). At the end of the month, the energy retailer sends the consumer the bill for the physical consumption of energy. The consumer also receives a breakdown from the RES developer showing the result of the financial adjustment (consumer needs to pay or receives) for the difference between the spot price and the agreed PPA price. Additionally, the developer will transfer the guarantees of origin generated by the installation to the consumer. It serves reducing the customers carbon footprint and works across national boundaries. The approach is valid since electrons are fungible and therefore undistinguishable in an open grid.
- **Sleeved PPA**
An agreement with a retailer is reached to transfer the conditions of the PPA signed between another client and the renewable developer to the consumer. This type of PPA permits agreeing on the consumed energy and permits making available contractually agreed, but not consumed capacities to the market via a retailer. This type of PPA is not available in all countries and across country borders.

Off-site PPAs depending on how the energy is delivered:

- **As-generated (or as-produced) PPA**
The consumer accepts the gross generation from the plant. This is the most competitive product when it comes to price; however, it is also the riskiest product for the consumer as generation from renewable sources is not predictable. It is only recommended for the consumers who have the capacities, knowledge and experience to manage well the offered energy and their loads and the excess and missing capacities. This can for instance be achieved with onsite battery-based energy storage systems.
- **Baseload PPA**
The renewable developer converts the gross generation from the plant into a duration-based pre-defined volume (yearly, monthly, weekly, daily, hourly) called "baseload". The consumer agrees to buy a total

volume of energy over a period spanning typically a few years. The volumes are in turn agreed for a defined period (usually annually, quarterly, or monthly). Profile and volume risks are with the seller who may be the developer or an intermediary entity. If the seller cannot meet its obligations through its plants, the agreed volume will be sourced from the spot market. This is the most common product, as there is an interesting balance between cost and risk. This type of PPA permits consuming an overall agreed capacity for a particular period of time (e.g. over one or several years) with varying consumption pattern. However, not all developers are able (lack of diversification) or willing to offer this type of PPA.

- **As-consumed PPA**

The renewable developer converts the gross generation into a curve which mirrors the customer consumption curve to an extent to be agreed. This is the most common product among non-expert customers as this is the product in which the developer gives most added value to the customer. Only companies with a large and diversified generation portfolio (e.g. onshore and offshore wind and PV) can compete in this type of PPA.

For a new research infrastructure with an FCC class particle accelerator, **a set of stacked PPAs will have to be considered**. Such a stack would likely be composed of different types of PPAs that will need to be periodically renewed. At any point in time a set of different PPAs would be active.

According to the consultants who carried out the feasibility analysis, **the most suited contract type is an off-site physical PPA** (as produced or baseload, depending on availability and portfolio management strategy).

In addition, to protect against exposure to volatile electricity spot market prices due to the need to complement the missing residual electricity not available in the frame of PPAs, **additional financially settled PPAs can be considered. They cover electricity certificate procurement on time scales between a quarter of a year and one year**. In such type of contract, the supplier pays to the customer in case the market price exceeds the agreed electricity prize. On the contrary, the customer pays the difference between the market prize and the settled prize if the market prize is low. The exact strike price levels are subject to commercial negotiations. Such an instrument can lower the overall electricity bill by offsetting non-consumed electricity and more expensive short-term needed electricity.

Standardised contract models for such types of PPAs exist in Europe including France¹².

Further PPA types can be considered to complement with additional capacities. The establishment of a PPA portfolio **includes market exposure risks that must be assumed and monitored after careful evaluation**. For instance, depending on the capability to faithfully estimate future consumptions, as-consumed PPAs can also be considered as complementary products to obtain additional limited capacities if situations of unconsumed, but contracted volumes can be avoided.

¹² European Federation of Energy Traders, Individual Power Purchase Agreement for Corporates and Utilities, <https://www.efet.org/files/documents/EFET%20Power%20Purchase%20Agreement%20Full%20Version%202019%20-%2004.11.2021.pdf>

3. MOTIVATION AND GOALS

The motivation to supply the FCC with RES is to present a long-term sustainable project scenario with planning security. Sustainability, "*the ability to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs*"¹³, simplified as "*the ability to be maintained at a certain rate or level*"¹⁴ includes diverse aspects such as greenhouse gas emission footprint, the capability to physically obtain energy and the long-term assurance of funding nations to be able to financially maintain the research infrastructure programme.

The goals for the study were to obtain answers to the following questions:

- To which extent can the FCC be powered from RES?
- What are the key challenges to supply the FCC with RES and how can they be overcome?
- What is the preferred scenario to source renewable energy for the FCC?
- Do CERN and the participating nations need to contribute with venture capital to supply the FCC with RES?
- What are credible cost targets for different RES coverage levels for the FCC?
- What is a credible timeline to supply the FCC with RES?
- Does supplying the FCC with RES lead to societal benefits? If yes, which ones?

The exploratory study with two consultancy companies Accenture and McKinsey who are active in the field of planning and developing renewable energy source supplies for industries and institutional clients including governments were both able to answer all questions coherently and consistently. The conclusions of the two independent investigations are summarised in Chapter 1.

Considering the encouraging results of the study, the investigations were enlarged to ask if not only FCC could be powered by renewable energy sources, but if the entire CERN during the FCC construction and operation phases could be subject to supply with renewable energy sources. This question was also positively answered. Section 11 highlights some already ongoing industrial RES sourcing activities that exceeds the FCC energy needs by one order of magnitude already today.

¹³ A Dictionary of Environment and Conservation, 3 ed. Oxford University Press, 2017, eISBN 9780191826320 and also the "United Nations Brundtland Commission" 1987, <http://www.un-documents.net/our-common-future.pdf>

¹⁴ Oxford English Dictionary

4. FCC ENERGY NEEDS

The assumed electricity needs serving as an input to the RES exploration study covered the weekly total load profiles of CERN during the FCC-ee planning, construction and operation phases. This includes the energy needs of CERN's current particle accelerators. Electricity need estimates are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Average annual electricity needs provided as input to RES study in 2022. The actual CERN and FCC needs are assumed to be less, since the values indicate theoretical energy need ceilings.

The FCC-ee specific needs and the average annual consumption estimates are summarized in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Unoptimized initial electricity capacity and particle collider facility consumption estimates in 2022 for different FCC-ee phases. The indicated annual quantities (TWh/year) represent upper limits.

FCC periods	Construction	Z Operation	W Operation	H Operation	Long shutdown	TT Operation	Upgrade
Beam energy (GeV)		45.6	80	120		182.5	
Exploitation period	2036-2044	2045-2048	2049-2050	2051-2053	2054	2055-2059	2060-2064
Max power (MW)	50	237	263	292	65	385	50
Min power (MW)	20	65	68	69	65	78	50
Annual energy consumption (TWh)	0.4	1.3	1.43	1.58	0.57	2.07	0.44

An extended project schedule starting before 2030 and covering the entire CERN electricity need estimates during the FCC-ee period was included in the study to provide an answer to the question as of when RES can be integrated into CERN's operation to increase the sustainability significantly starting with the FCC construction phase.

CERN's energy needs range today between 1.0 and 1.3 TWh per year when operating the existing particle accelerators and about 0.6 TWh during years when maintaining those particle accelerators. It may approach about 1.6 TWh around 2029 with the upgrade of the LHC experiments, the HL-LHC and a new data centre. CERN's total energy needs during the FCC-ee era with the operation of other proton physics research facilities such as the SPS north area and all Meyrin site would vary between 0.6 TWh and at most 2.6 TWh per year, depending on the choice of the operated facilities. The total peak consumption would not exceed 2.6 TWh during the FCC-ee ttbar operation mode around 2055.

The average annual energy need of the FCC-ee complex during its lifetime is around 1.5 TWh per year.

5. SUPPLY OPTIONS

With respect to technologies the following renewable energy sources including nuclear energy as de-carbonised energy source were investigated with the following results:

- **Offshore wind: very suitable**
- **Onshore wind: suitable** as complementary source
- **Solar photovoltaic power: suitable** as complementary source
- Hydroelectric power: unsuitable
- Biomass: unsuitable
- Geothermal energy: unsuitable
- Tidal power: unsuitable
- Nuclear power: limited complementary suitability during the transition to RES
- Hydrogen fired gas turbines: limited complementary suitability during the transition to RES

Figure 2: A selection of exemplary offshore, onshore and solar power sources planned and recently brought in operation in Europe. It can be seen from the map that the individual RES plant capacities match well the range of the energy that an FCC requires and that therefore future developments of additional renewable energy sources are technically well adapted to provide the required capacities if the electricity is accessible via the national grid in France. Source: Accenture RES study for FCC, 2023.

CERN is well located to use electricity from renewable energy sources (see Figure 2). Due to the potentials in France, the planned and emerging developments in this country and the foreseeable technological progress, **offshore wind power has been identified as the most suitable renewable energy source** for the FCC. By the time of FCC construction start around 2035, the national offshore wind capacity in Europe is estimated to be around 260 GW with 18 GW in France. By the time FCC-ee operates in 2045, the capacity is foreseen to be above 510 GW in Europe and at 34 GW in France.

Onshore wind is a well-established technology in Europe with lower annual growth factors than offshore wind. Its supply reliability and per unit efficiency will also remain lower than offshore wind. Onshore wind plants

require substantial land allocation. Therefore, in France the prevalence of onshore wind power production is so far modest. Still, by 2035 a capacity of 31 GW and by 2045 a capacity of 35 GW can be expected, **permitting to complement** the offshore supply in form of an energy mix to improve the supply reliability.

Solar photovoltaic power has the **highest capacity compared to the other RES** exceeding a capacity of 1 TW by 2040 in Europe. By 2035 the installed capacity in France is expected to be 68 GW and by 2045 a capacity of 100 GW is expected. It has by far the **lowest operation cost**. However, the low annual utilisation factor and the accessibility to the vast amounts of solar energy from neighbouring countries due to the limited transnational electricity grid capacities and the regulatory constraints remain challenges. However, the new 5 GW connection between Spain and France¹⁵ to become operational around 2027, providing about 48 TWh of annual exchange capacity can remedy the situation if PPA suppliers can obtain transnational electricity transfer line capacities. Battery-based energy storage can largely compensate for the utilisation factor limitation. The technology can **complement the offshore and onshore wind** power sources in a RES mix to achieve long-stable energy supply and cost targets.

Hydropower is already mature in Europe and has very limited expansion potentials. Bioenergy is associated with limited expansion potentials and significant costs. Geothermal energy has limited capacity. The supply of planned tidal power is not significant. Therefore, these technologies are considered unsuitable for the FCC.

Nuclear energy is today the major power source for CERN. This technology is reliable (24/7 coverage) but it has also the highest levelized cost of electricity (see Figure 3) of all energy sources. Due to its construction costs and duration, maintenance intensity, the aging of existing plants and the decommissioning costs, the economic downturn is expected to remain¹⁶. The levelized cost of electricity of hydrogen gas fired turbines, another de-carbonised energy source, is in the same prize range.

A mix of renewable energy sources (offshore, onshore, solar) is foreseen to outperform nuclear energy and hydrogen fired gas turbines before the end of this decade. Nuclear energy and hydrogen fired gas turbines maintain the advantage of a high utilisation factor, **permitting to assure electricity supply when renewable energy sources are not able to deliver**. However, **on a mid-term to long-term time scale it is likely to also assure electricity supply with limited duration, battery-based energy storage solutions**. Onshore wind and solar energy are already cheaper than nuclear and hydrogen gas fired turbine energy if contracted for on a long-term basis today.

Summing up, **the national RES capacities in France will exceed the FCC needs by almost a factor of 1 000 when the FCC is planned to start operation**. Compared to the total electricity provision via the French national grid in 2021, the FCC needs are 0.4 permille. With respect to complementing energy from national RES with renewable energy with transnational electricity access, the FCC needs would be in the permille range of the 2021¹⁷ recorded French electricity import and can therefore be considered marginal on the relevant time scale.

¹⁵ <https://www.rte-france.com/projets/nos-projets/golfe-de-gascogne>

¹⁶ The production cost of energy at the Flamanville-3 plant is estimated between 110 and 120 EUR/MWh. Plant operation has been re-scheduled to 2024. <https://www.enerdata.net/publications/daily-energy-news/flamanville-3-nuclear-projects-cost-may-rise-eu67bn-france.html>

¹⁷ Factsheet of the ENTSO-E (European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity) transparency platform 2021, <https://www.entsoe.eu/data/power-stats/>

The LCOE ranges shown in Figure 3 are fully in line with the costs reported by the UK government report on electricity generation costs 2023¹⁸ and with the report from the European Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on the progress on competitiveness of clean energy technologies in 2022¹⁹.

Progress on competitiveness of clean energy technologies

Figure 3: LCOE evolution range estimates of renewable and de-carbonised energy sources across entire Europe. The ranges indicate the maximum and minimum projections from the multiple sources indicated. The ranges from maximum to minimum account for factors such as weather conditions, capacity factors, CO2 certificate prices. Solar PV is assumed on utility scale. Sources: Accenture analysis, IEA (2021), Fraunhofer Institute (2021); Statista (2022); Solarify (2022); wegatech (2022), world-nuclear (2023); IRENA (2022), U.S. DoE NREL (2022), European Commission SET Plan (2021). The LCOE does not represent actual market prices.

The overall annual capacity utilization factors of around 45% for wind and 25% for solar power throughout the year permit achieving up to 80% could be covered with RES using a set of off-site Power Purchase Agreements (PPA). The contract scenarios are presented in the next chapter.

¹⁸ UK, Department for Energy Security & Net Zero, "Electricity generation costs 2023", https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1179359/electricity-generation-costs-2023.pdf

¹⁹ EC, "Progress on competitiveness of clean energy technologies", COM(2022), 641, Brussels 15.11.2022, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52022DC0643&qid=1669913060946>

6. CONTRACT SCENARIOS

Concluding a set of long-term (order of 10 to 15 years) off-site physical wind power PPAs **permits covering more than 60% of CERN's electricity needs for the FCC observation period**. The independent estimates of power purchasing market professionals for planning and concluding such contracts requires several years, excluding organisation internal process associated times (e.g. strategy decision, team establishment, procurement actions, negotiations, decision taking). Supply and demand mismatches can for instance be mitigated by including market transactions for excess renewable energy and buying missing energy with financial PPAs (see example in Figure 4). According to the consultants, a baseload contract may be defined on different time basis, annual, monthly, or even according to a load profile. An as-produced PPA can be used to assure a certain level of the energy needs. Financial PPAs can be used to hedge against the exposure to the volatile market prize to complement the residual capacities. Energy storage can compensate for the limited utilisation factor and lower the electricity cost. Detailed information about the operation schedule and its variability are required to be able to carry out specific and detailed simulations to define the most suitable contract type which may also be a hybrid between baseload and as-produced to provide balancing and shaping services. All conditions need to be individually developed, tendered and negotiated. This requires significant lead times, diligent contract preparation, financial exposure risk monitoring and active contract management.

Figure 4: Example for a simplistic RES supply scenario with an off-site physical PPA that is complemented with buying and selling additional energy on the market. The contract type in which these transactions happen is not specified here. The additional transactions may be included in the PPA or in a separate contract. Development of the PPA and contract portfolio requires more detailed knowledge about the FCC construction phase and an operation schedule. Deviations from the schedule may also be included in the PPA conditions but will result in cost increase due to the suppliers' economic risk mitigation needs. The contractual details call for the involvement of experienced energy procurement experts, either by building an in-house group, outsourcing to a dedicated company or a combination of the two. Source: McKinsey RES supply study for FCC, 2023.

Adding a solar energy component permits covering 80% the FCC era electricity needs with excess capacities that can be sold to the market to offset the cost of additional grid energy and the residual carbon footprint. Since such a scenario contains a moderate exposure to the electricity market, a conservative price estimate foresees a 15% cost increase of the PPA energy cost per MWh with respect to the initial scenario.

Complementing the portfolio with onshore wind energy would bring RES coverage up to 95% at the cost of 35% increase of the electricity unit prize per MWh with respect to the initial scenario. As above, the cost increase is due to the mitigation of the market exposure risk if excess energy needs to be put on the market by the developer or retailer at prizes that are lower than agreed.

Unless the entire electricity grid is fully de-carbonised there will always be a residual component of energy of unknown origin. Residual components (40% in a baseline scenario, 20% in an intermediary scenario and 5% in an advanced scenario) can under today's conditions be offset with financial (virtual) PPAs. This contract type serves purchasing renewable energy certificates (no energy flows from the supplier to the customer) in addition to the existing electricity contracts on the open European market, which can be re-sold by the organisation. The certificate trading permits hedging against volatile short term electricity prizes, lowering the total electricity bill and serves achieving full RES coverage due to guarantees of origin at the cost of overall increased market risk exposure. The approach is valid since electrons are fungible and therefore undistinguishable in the open grid. For a taxpayer funded international organisation the conditions of this type of financial instrument remain under today's applicable conditions to be carefully assessed.

Figure 5: Example for a stepping up a portfolio of 9 individual PPAs using a set of off-site physical PPAs. Depending on the contract durations, calls for contract renewals must be included. The initial PPAs would include a nuclear energy component. In addition to the physical contracts, further contracts for market supply and complementary PPA types are necessary to achieve high coverage with RES at competitive price under adequate, flexible operation conditions. This feasibility study did not include a PPA contract planning exercise since today incomplete knowledge about the electricity needs, potential suppliers and contractual conditions is available in France. The scheme is therefore intended for illustrative purposes only. The scheme shows, however, that management of many concurrent contracts calls for a dedicated and experienced team or the contracting of a contract management office. Source: Accenture RES supply study FCC, 2023.

Covering FCCs electricity needs during the construction and operation phases after 2035, starting with 0.5 TWh per year would likely permit RES coverage that approaches eventually the 100% level (Figure 5).

To provide evidence for the contract feasibility, consider a selection of individual RES PPA deals concluded in Europe in 2022. Figure 6 below shows the capacities covered by the deals in MW and indicates the FCC-ee needs from 2045 onwards, i.e., in more than 20 years. The figure shows that procurement of renewable energy in Europe at the required scales is already possible today. Companies throughout Europe use by now regularly such PPAs to hedge against electricity prize volatility.

Figure 6: Selection of renewable energy source PPAs by buyers concluded in Europe in 2022, indicating the covered capacities and the FCC-ee capacity needs between 2045 and 2060. Source: Pexapark, European PPA market outlook 2023, V9. The majority of RES PPAs concluded are and will remain to be linked to the IT sector, followed by metals & mining. Together they account for two thirds of the RES PPA market in Europe.

Temporary **offsite or onsite energy storage in the two-to-six-hour range** may be considered in all scenarios, which would increase the RES coverage and lower costs. Emerging battery technologies are suitable. Today the capacity for storing at least one hour of 200 MW exists on the market using refurbished electric vehicle batteries that are assembled to form individual 25 MWh energy storage units. One such unit at each surface site would yield a total of 200 MWh already today (see Figure 7), leveraging circular economy principles. **Today's largest battery-based energy storage system with a capacity of 1 300 MWh²⁰ already satisfies the entire FCC needs.** A total lifecycle analysis is required to be able to analyse if an integrated sustainability advantage (cost plus environmental impact) over a single conventional electricity supply source exists. Cost evolution estimates of utility-scale Li-ion (LIB) storage systems are periodically made available by the U.S. DoE^{21,22}. Sodium-ion (Na-ion or NIB) batteries entering the market now are well-suited for electricity storage systems that are not

²⁰ Huawei 1 300 MWh Red Sea BESS installed in 2023: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UocajzLUauI>

²¹ W. Cole, A.W. Frazier and C. Augustine, Cost Projections for Utility-Scale Battery Storage: 2021 Update, NREL/TP-6A20-79236, U.S. Department of Energy, National Renewable Energy Laboratory, June 2021. Online available at <https://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy21osti/79236.pdf>

²² U.S. Department of Energy, National Renewable Energy Laboratory, Annual Technology Baseline, Utility-Scale Battery Storage, Bottom-up Cost Model for CAPEX and OPEX, 2022, Online available at: https://atb.nrel.gov/electricity/2022/utility-scale_battery_storage

determined by weight and real-estate constraints. They are made from raw materials that are less expensive, more abundant and less toxic. Another asset is their ability to be fully charged and fully discharged without risk of altering the performance. Their cost reduction potential with respect to Li-ion systems is significant²³. Other energy storage technologies are considered less suitable to the FCC needs due to their technical limitations and costs. Pumped storage for hydropower remains a valid option for long-term energy storage in the 24-hour range. It would need to be contracted based on existing capacities. The costs associated with the creation of new capacities are prohibitive and the opportunities for locations are very limited.

Very recently²⁴, so called "energy storage" or "hybrid" RES PPAs emerge that include the offsite storage capability in the contract. First deployments appear in combination with PV plants, coupled with dedicated batteries in the 600 MWh range, i.e. half of the FCC energy buffering needs. Such a configuration starts to enter the range that fits the FCC-ee requirements.

Figure 7: A single 25 MWh energy storage unit (white containers) built from used electric car batteries, deployed for a PV energy plant in Lancaster, CA (south of Los Angeles, US) put in operate by B2U Storage Solutions in early 2023. Capacities of new systems are increasing fast. A 260 MWh²⁵ is by now being commissioned and today's largest systems in the range of 1 400 MWh are being extended to 3 000 MWh²⁶.

All additional grid electricity costs, conditions for selling excess energy together with their electricity strike prizes and collars are subject to negotiation after diligent preparation with economic performance simulations that rely on the particle collider construction and annual operation schedules. Requirements for dynamic changes and flexibilities need to be carefully defined based on economic risk acceptance and mitigation criteria. For this to happen, the performance targets need to be set with respect to environmental, social and governance (ESG) behaviour goals that need to be balanced with economic performance goals.

CERN's long-term commitment and foreseeable operation programme are considered excellent levers for such negotiations, permitting experienced energy buyers obtaining very adequate conditions and prizes with respect to common commercial and industrial offtakes who are dominated by more severe constraints.

²³ J.F. Peters, A.P. Cruz and M. Weil, "Exploring the Economic Potential of Sodium-Ion Batteries", Batteries 2019, 5(1), 10; <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries5010010>

²⁴ <https://www.businesswire.com/news/home/20210902005919/en/EDF-Renewables-North-America-and-Clean-Power-Alliance-Sign-Power-Purchase-Agreement-for-Solar-plus-Storage-Project>

²⁵ <https://www.energy-storage.news/texas-largest-battery-project-to-date-brought-online-by-vistra/>

²⁶ <https://www.energy-storage.news/expansion-plan-to-take-worlds-biggest-battery-storage-project-to-3gwh-capacity/>

7. COST TARGET

The **cost target** is based on 2022 and 2023 levelized cost of electricity (LCOE²⁷) for renewable energy sources and for the **volumes required by CERN with the FCC-ee in the year 2045**. For long term RES PPAs **the total cost of electricity is predictable and stable over the PPA period. Due to the long-term engagement between developer and buyer, the prizes are considered to eventually approach the LCOE plus a revenue margin, transmission and distribution overheads, since the developer has a guaranteed long-term cash flow and only little investment risks²⁸.**

For a working hypothesis of covering 80% of the electricity needs with renewable energy sources, the **non-inflation adjusted long term cost estimate for electricity solely from French territory is 50 euros per MWh²⁹** based on the consensus results of analysis carried out by two consulting companies³⁰ and following evidence of the evolution of RES auctions traced between 2012 and 2021 (see Figure 5). **France has brought an initial guarantee fund into operation in 2023** to help assuring a stable electricity prize for 15 to 25 years long RES PPAs for a total of up to 500 MW of capacities³¹. It is expected that such kind of incentives continue to be developed and put in place to accelerate the transition to sustainable energy sources and to protect the market against price volatility.

²⁷ LCOE is a measure for the average net present cost of electricity generation over the entire lifetime for the generator. It includes all related costs including the plant, operation and maintenance, financing, utilisation rate, management, and decommissioning. It represents the total average revenue per unit of electricity generated that would be required to recover all related costs during the entire financial life of the generating source.

²⁸ Wind and solar parks are among the large-scale projects without or with only little cost and time overruns due to their modular characteristics. The investment costs are very predictable and steadily falling. Operation, maintenance, and repair costs are also steadily decreasing with ever larger wind turbines and higher efficiency solar panels. Contracted excess energy not consumed by the buyer can be put on the market and depending on the PPA conditions the market exposure risk sharing between developer, retailer and consumer can be tuned.

²⁹ For comparison, EDF has been chosen on 27 March 2023 to construct and operate the "Centre Marche 1" 1GW capacity offshore wind park. The facility is planned to enter operation in 2031. The electricity offtake price has been set to 50 euros/MWh by the ministry of ecological transition. More information at <https://www.edf.fr/groupe-edf/espaces-dedies/journalistes/tous-les-communiqués-de-presse/le-groupe-edf-et-maple-power-rempoortent-un-projet-eolien-en-mer-dun-gigawatt-au-large-de-la-normandie> and about the park at www.parc-eolien-en-mer-manche-normandie.fr

³⁰ For comparison, the market averaged continental PPA price index published by LevelTen for blended wind and solar was 75 EUR/MWh in Q3 2022. The solar power index for France was approximatively 73 EUR/MWh.

³¹ <https://www.economie.gouv.fr/energie-renouvelable-nouveau-fonds-garantie-contrats-appvisionnement>

Figure 8: Real contracted PPA prizes (tariff levels) in the frame of RES project auctions between 2012 and 2021 in Europe. The left graph shows the auction results of 503 RES projects in Europe. The right graph shows only the auction results of 91 onshore and offshore wind plants in that period. The last average PPA prize for all new RES projects was 90 euro/MWh and 60 euro/MWh for wind energy. Source: AURES II RES auction database, EU H2020 co-funded project, GA 817619³².

It should be noted that in November 2020 an initial number of nine EU countries has committed on reaching an LCOE target of 35 to 45 Euro/MWh by 2030 for offshore wind³³. This "fair value" target includes a 5% to 10% margin for the PPA suppliers. Long-term LCOE for the FCC-ee supply scenario is expected to drop from initially 52 euro per MWh to about 32 euro until the end of the FCC-ee operation phase towards 2060 (see Figure 9). The fair value excludes transport and distribution fees and taxes. It applies, however, to the total energy coverage needed, supplementing wind and solar offsite RES PPAs with buying from and selling to the market the residual fraction. **Adding energy storage such as on-site or off-site batteries would reduce the cost target by 5% to 15% depending on the installed capacity and technology, permitting at the same time to increase RES coverage significantly to 95% and avoiding market exposure.** McKinsey estimated that increasing RES coverage under today's conditions without complementary RES supplies and battery storage would lead to a prize uncertainty of up to 78 euro per MWh revenue margins without transmission and distribution overheads and taxes due to the dependence on economic boundary conditions, demand and supply situation and daily unforeseeable trading factors for the additional energy needed that is not covered by the PPAs. **78 euros per MWh, which is in the range of the recent continental wind PPA auction prizes (see Figure 5) can be used as an upper cost boundary for the electricity cost for the starting of the FCC construction phase.**

³² AURES II, H2020 co-funded EU project, RES auction database online available at <http://aures2project.eu>

³³ The European Strategic Energy Technology Plan Targets and objectives, online available at https://setis.ec.europa.eu/implementing-actions/wind-energy_en

Expected LCOE spread of technology mix for initial contracting rounds

Figure 9: Estimate of the LCOE evolution for an offshore/onshore/PV RES mix until 2055. A midpoint around 50 euro/MWh is used as an LCOE working hypothesis. The 2018 - 2021 wind PPA auction prize averages in Europe are already approaching this range, since auction prizes include revenue margins on top of the LCOE. Source: Accenture RES study for FCC, February 2023.

Additional supply-associated fees apply. They vary over the years depending on the grid connection contractual conditions, the amount of energy consumed and saved and the evolution of the legal and regulatory framework and depending on how they apply to the international organisation. From past and current operation at CERN the typical additional, supply-related cost elements³⁴ to be considered are:

- TURPE³⁵, the "tarif d'acheminement de l'électricité", a fee to be paid for the use of the public electricity distribution grid that is used to operate, maintain and improve the network. The fees are regulated by the French national "Commission de Régulation de l'énergie" (CRE).
- CEE³⁶, the "Certificats d'économies d'énergie", a French national energy savings certificate anchored as a law is a system intended to oblige consumers to implement energy savings. The certificates can be traded such that consumers who perform energy savings have an advantage over other consumers. If energy suppliers are not able to gather a specific number of certificates from their consumers, penalty payments apply to the supplier who in turn forward them to those consumers who failed to achieve the energy savings goals.
- Capacity certificates³⁷, a system that has been put in place in France in 2017 serves assuring a sufficient electricity supply capacity during the winter season. Reserve electricity generation plants need to be established and maintained to be able to cover those peak periods, even if the capacities are not used during off peak seasons. The cost for these capacities is covered via the capacity certificates. The mechanism is anchored in the "Code de l'Énergie" law. Certificates are traded on the European market.

For a supply with electricity from renewable energy sources it is today not possible to estimate with sufficient detail the costs that need to be added to the PPA prize. Certain contributions reaching 10% of the energy costs, such as the TURPE will be invoiced, but since CERN is already today ISO 50001³⁸ energy management system certified, a large part of that cost is re-imbursed at the end of the accounting period resulting in a net 1% to 2% additional fee. Considering that renewable energy benefits typically from cost advantages, the CEE part can today not be easily estimated. It can make up between 10% and 15% of the electricity consumed. Finally, the capacity obligation can range from 0% to 7%, depending on the capacity utilisation factor of the energy source, the amount of excess energy available during the peak consumption season and on the actual use during the

³⁴ https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/Datalab_essentiel%20prix_elec_2021_051022_TD_bis_0.pdf

³⁵ <https://www.services-rte.com/en/learn-more-about-our-services/understanding-the-public-transmission-system-access-tariff-turpe.html>

³⁶ <https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/dispositif-des-certificats-deconomies-denergie>

³⁷ https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/codes/article_lc/LEGIARTI000043215179

³⁸ <https://home.cern/news/news/cern/managing-energy-responsibly-cern-awarded-iso-50001-certification>

peak consumption season (e.g. shift of particle collider operation between winter and summer). Historically, the total additional fees for electricity for CERN were between 10% and 20% of the per MWh energy cost.

For the FCC-ee period we assume conservatively **20% of additional fees on top of the PPA target prize of 50 euro per MWh**. That brings the **total cost to about 60 euro per MWh (50 euro + 20%)**. The **likely scenario is a higher initial PPA prize in the order of 55 euro per MWh that gradually decreases with additional PPAs** as more renewable energy sources and storage are brought in.

Having the **possibility to tap into competitively priced complementary solar energy from southern countries** (e.g. Spain) and **offshore wind power from northern countries** (e.g. Germany, Denmark) would **permit lowering the cost target** by 5 to 10 euro per MWh to around 40 euro per MWh. Today, however, the transnational access to electricity from RES in Europe is still limited by the transnational line capacities and regulatory energy exchange constraints. Customers have today no direct physical access to transnational electricity exchange systems and capacity reservations are subject to short-term trading and high price volatility. **EU policy support for Research Infrastructures and accelerated pan-European electricity infrastructure development are required** to remedy the situation at least partially. Page 16 of the French energy and climate strategy published in 2023³⁹ mentions that France and Germany commit themselves to strengthen the exchange of renewable energy, in particular originating from solar and wind power. Strengthening of the energy exchange infrastructure with the Benelux countries, with Spain and with Portugal are also on the priority list of France. Article L100-1 of the law for the energy transition⁴⁰ includes the contribution to the establishment of a European energy union.

CERN as an international organisation and system-relevant, strategic research infrastructure would be in a good position to serve as a case to contribute to the advancement of the regulatory framework for pan-European trans-border electricity access according to the consultants' analysis. Policy support at highest national and international levels are required to engage a process. Considering that the complementary energy needs to be sourced from neighbouring countries will remain limited and that these volumes are marginal with respect to the transnational electricity transmission capacities, the consultants consider the possibility to source residual electricity from other countries a feasible scenario.

Procuring and **managing a portfolio of PPAs via an external intermediary service would increase the cost by 5 to 10 euro per MWh** and permits also transferring market exposure risks to the intermediary. A more complete analysis is necessary to make a strategic choice between working with an external service for the management of the PPA portfolio and to have an in-house team of **specifically hired market experienced staff**. **Such a scenario does not cover the actual trading of excess electricity, which would remain in the realm of the PPA suppliers and energy brokers.**

To provide specific and **credible evidence for the stated cost target**, we refer to the first offshore **wind auction held in France by the government in July 2020**. It concerned a total capacity of 1 GW divided into four projects⁴¹, corresponding to the capacity target to cover CERN and the FCC-ee by 2045. The four projects were located off the coasts⁴² of Normandy and Brittany and were expected to generate in total enough electricity to power around 1.5 million homes. The auction was based on a competitive process where bidders submitted their proposals for the lowest price that they were willing to accept for the electricity generated by their wind farms over a period of 20 years. The auction attracted major players in the offshore wind industry, including EDF

³⁹ *Stratégie française pour l'énergie et le climat. Programmation pluriannuelle de l'énergie 2024-2028*. Paris: Ministère de la Transition Ecologique et Solidaire.

⁴⁰ Code de l'énergie. France: Légifrance, le service public de la diffusion du droit, 25 August 2021.

⁴¹ <https://www.eoliennesenmer.fr/facades-maritimes-en-france/facade-manche-mer-du-nord/projet-centre-manche>

⁴² <https://fr.rwe.com/eolien-en-mer/projets-en-france/la-manche/>

Renewables, Shell, Equinor, and Iberdrola. The winning bids ranged from 44.8 to 52.4 euros per MWh with **eventual market price rates between 44 and 60 euros per MWh for a period of 20 years**⁴³.

For comparison, the current ARENH law obliges EDF to sell up to 100 TWh from nuclear power generation per year at a regulated price of 42 euros per MWh. This instrument will be discontinued in 2025⁴⁴.

Another example is the 605 MW, 51% CUF per year offshore Kriegers Flak⁴⁵ wind farm in Denmark. Tendered in 2015, the non-inflation adjusted price for the electricity supplied by this infrastructure was set to **49.9 euro/MWh in 2016**. The farm became **operational 5 years later in 2021**. Construction took 4 years from May 2018 to end 2021. It is today's cheapest offshore wind deal and demonstrates the maintained trend of rapidly falling costs in offshore wind power.

At the indicated total prize target of 60 euro per MWh, the **overall average annual electricity cost of CERN including the FCC-ee operation phase (2045 – 2060) are about 120 million euro per year**. From the construction phase to the end of the FCC-ee operation phase (2035 – 2060), the **annual FCC related electricity costs are expected to be about 60 million euro per year**. Figure 10 shows the estimated cost for each year for FCC and for the entire CERN infrastructure.

Figure 10: Estimated annual electricity costs for CERN with the FCC (x axis) in million euros (y axis).

The cost for the tt operation phase is expected to be lower than for the initial operation phase, since by that time cheaper electricity from solar energy sources at national level and via the new transnational electricity line with Spain will be available and battery-based energy storage at the needed capacity is likely to be available at competitive prize.

⁴³ <https://www.cre.fr/Documents/Deliberations/Avis/projet-de-cahier-des-charges-relatif-a-la-procedure-de-mise-en-concurrence-avec-dialogue-concurrentiel-n-1-2020-portant-sur-des-installations-eolie>

⁴⁴ <https://www.edf.fr/entreprises/electricite-gaz/le-benefice-arenh>

⁴⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kriegers_Flak

8. CARBON FOOTPRINT AND CONSUMPTION IN RELATION

The carbon equivalent footprint (CO₂e⁴⁶) for the electricity that CERN and the FCC require can be estimated based on the guidelines established by Ademe (www.ademe.fr), the French organisation for the ecological transition. The CO₂e footprint of the use of electricity is part of the so called "indirect" Scope 2 emissions. They constitute a part of the total greenhouse gas footprint that is composed by Scope 1, 2 and 3 emissions.

As a basis, the reported and assumed CO₂e emissions are associated with the entire lifecycle of an energy source. The values shown in Table 2 have been used to estimate the carbon equivalent footprint associated with the electricity use during the FCC-ee programme period. This approach serves purely illustrative purposes providing an indication of the order of magnitude and must not be directly compared to the results of a proper integrating greenhouse gas study using an accredited method such as Bilan Carbone[®] used for CERN's environment reports⁴⁷.

Table 2: CO₂e footprint of different electricity energy sources.

Energy source	CO ₂ e emission	Source
Offshore wind power (full lifecycle)	15.6 t/GWh	La Base Empreinte ^{®48} for 2020 to 2023
Onshore wind power (full lifecycle)	14.1 t/GWh	La Base Empreinte [®] for 2013
Photovoltaic (full lifecycle, national production)	25.2 t/GWh	La Base Empreinte [®] until 2024
National market electricity mix	56.9 t/GWh	La Base Empreinte [®] 2021

The CO₂e footprint associated with the FCC-ee electricity consumption has been estimated for a baseload coverage of 80% renewable energy sources and with complementary electricity from unknown origin (energy source mix) bought from the market (see Table 3).

Table 3: Estimated CO₂e footprint associated with FCC-ee electricity consumption based on 80% RES coverage.

Consumer	CO ₂ e emission
CERN with FCC-ee for the 15 years FCC-ee operation phase	814 920 t
FCC-ee only for its 15-years long operation phase	600 385 t
CERN with FCC-ee per year for the 15 years FCC-ee operation phase	54 328 t
FCC-ee only per year for its 15-years long operation phase	40 026 t

⁴⁶ Carbon dioxide equivalent or CO₂e means the number of metric tons of CO₂ emissions with the same global warming potential as one metric ton of another greenhouse gas, by converting amounts of other (Kyoto) gases (e.g. CH₄, N₂O, HFCs, PFCs, SF₆, NF₃) to the equivalent amount of carbon dioxide with the same global warming potential using conversion factors established by notified bodies. The conversion factor for carbon dioxide (CO₂) is 1.

⁴⁷ <https://hse.cern/environment-report-2019-2020>

⁴⁸ <https://base-empreinte.ademe.fr>, registration and login required.

The figures outlined above must be put into relation with the 290.5 million taxpayers in the EU27 and an estimated total 510 million taxpayers globally who would financially contribute to an FCC programme (see Table 4). It is also important to recall that a CERN associated carbon footprint is already included in the annual account per person in France (11.2 t) and in Geneva (12.9 t) today and it is likely that this contribution is actually reduced due to continued efficiency increase, use of novel technologies and renewable energy sources. The CO₂e footprint is not an addition to CERN's CO₂e footprint today, since the FCC replaces the LHC and elements of its current injector chain.

Table 4: Typical person-related carbon footprint values.

Consumer	CO₂e
CO ₂ e footprint per astronomer in Australia (electricity only)	25 000 kg
CO ₂ e footprint per astronomer in Germany (electricity only)	5 200 kg
CO₂e footprint per researcher involved in the FCC programme per year	3 300 kg
CO ₂ e footprint of 1 hamburger	3 000 g
CO ₂ e footprint of 1 biscuit (from production to customer)	140 g
CO ₂ e footprint of 1 banana (from production to customer)	113 g
CO₂e footprint for each taxpayer contributing to CERN with the FCC-ee per year	106 g
CO₂e footprint for each taxpayer contributing to the FCC only per year	78 g
Boiling 1 water kettle	34 g
1 email with attachment	10 g
1 hour of Youtube usage per viewer	164 g
1 hour of Netflix usage per viewer	983 g
1 hour of Facebook interaction per user	16 g
1 hour of TikTok operation per user	328 g

With respect to the CO₂e footprint, the FCC-ee energy needs are in the range of the carbon footprints associated with the electricity consumption of a typical French national Internet Service Provider (ISP) or a national supermarket chain. As can be seen from Figure 11, the electricity consumption induced carbon footprint of CERN with an FCC-ee is dwarfed by general national telecom operators and Internet companies. Consumer driven data processing and data transmission are a major cause for carbon emissions today and are foreseen to be in the future⁴⁹. Agriculture and air traffic emissions are top CO₂e producers, too.

⁴⁹ <https://www.iea.org/reports/data-centres-and-data-transmission-networks>

Figure 11: Carbon footprint of selected organisations put in relation to the CO2e footprint induced by the FCC-ee electricity consumption. The two bold marked figures (54 328 t/year and 40 026 t/year) indicate the range of the CO2e emissions associated with the electricity consumption during of CERN with the FCC-ee programme. They are in the range of typical Internet Service Providers, national telecom operators, large cultural venues and national supermarket chains.

9. SOCIETAL AND ECONOMIC BENEFITS

Initiating a transition to source electricity from renewable energy sources creates at least the following societal benefits in addition to a lower carbon footprint and long-term electricity bill stability:

Accelerated energy transition: The series of long-term step-up contracts for FCC provides planning security for the electricity suppliers that lets them invest in building up significant renewable energy source capacities in the GW range for which only a fraction would be used for the FCC. The remaining capacities are made available for other clients, thus helping to speed up the energy transition and speeding up access to RES at competitive cost. The direct impact on GDP growth induced by the build-up of renewable energy sources in the GW range has been estimated by McKinsey to be in the range of 700 million euros for a period of 25 years.

Additional funds for the electricity industry: The exploratory study with the consultancy companies showed that the long-term predictable consumption of a publicly funded institution such as CERN permits energy suppliers to leverage funding for RES projects at more advantageous conditions as compared to standard project funding using bank loans based on hypothetical client and general market consumption forecasts.

Transnational power exchange improvement potential: The EC considers the improvement of the transnational power exchange via an evolution of the regulatory framework and the build-up of capacities a priority⁵⁰ to improve resilience and energy independence in Europe⁵¹. Today, the electricity market is limited by national policies and limited capacities between neighbouring countries, which are in addition dedicated to power balancing between countries and subject to monthly auctions with volatile prizes. Every additional project that helps making a further case to increase cohesion and provide additional reason for EU policy support has a potential to improve the transnational power exchange situation on a long-term perspective.

Excess green energy at competitive prize: Including market transactions in PPAs can result in more electricity from RES being put on the market than missing energy being bought if the RES coverage for FCC is above 60%. This leads to an immediate direct societal benefit if the excess energy is made available at a capped prize for instance for other institutional clients such as research institutes, universities or schools.

Sustainable creation of jobs: the long-term aim to source electricity from renewable energy sources over long periods of time translates directly into job creation. A study⁵² carried out by the Austrian Economics Research Institute (WIFO) in 2022 revealed that a renewable energy sourcing project for the FCC-ee has a potential to sustain 11 600 person years of employment, thereof 7 400 in Europe over a 25 years period.

Accelerated energy storage technology advancement: Introducing temporary storage of electricity increases further the RES coverage for FCC and lowers the price per MWh. These goals form a motivation to advance battery-based electricity storage technology in the 200 MW range for two to six hours, i.e. with a total capacity of 1 200 MWh. **CERN and the FCC can become an ideal showcase for Europe's innovation capacities.** This can also be a driver for circular economy initiatives such as the re-use of EV batteries and by advancing new battery technologies for societal added value in the entire energy value chain from the source to the consumer. Ultimately these developments become again societal and economic benefit enablers.

⁵⁰ EU announcement on 14 March 2023 online at https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_23_1591

⁵¹ RePowerEurope, online available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2022:230:FIN>

⁵² Streicher, Gerhard. (2023). Building CERN's Future Circular Collider. An Estimation of its Impact on Value Added and Employment (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7382706>

10. CLOSING REMARKS

This document presents a feasibility study to supply the FCC-ee with electricity from renewable energy sources during construction and operation phases. The analysis is based on a set of assumptions for the electricity needs and consumption profile. A few key enablers are required as prerequisites for this approach and both consultancy companies recommend some activities to continue the exploration of the presented approach:

1. **Initiate exchanges with potential RES developers on the feasibility conditions** and
2. **Seek policy support from the EU, national governments and investment enablers.**

McKinsey and Accenture identified together about fifteen energy developers that are interested to engage in exchanges on long-term strategy exploration including the development of new RES capacities. Such non-binding exchanges serve getting to a mutual understanding of the interests that are the basis for potential tendering processes at a much later stage. The objectives are:

- Identify energy source capacity development opportunities and the time scales.
- Refine price targets.
- Determine better the RES coverage potential based on the energy mix, the energy source locations, off-site/on-site storage components and contractual conditions.

Policy support exchanges in France and at EU at high level should be engaged for the following purposes:

1. At national and EU levels, make CERN's future energy needs clear in terms of capacities, load shapes, operation phases and flexibilities for adapting to supply patterns.
2. At EU level, understand the possibilities and conditions to ease access to transborder electricity access.
3. At EU level, facilitate the showcase of a scalable battery-based energy storage system with European technology and by leveraging circular economy principles.
4. At national level, understand the possibilities to support energy developers to gain access to seabed.
5. At investment bank level, develop a bidding process in cooperation with national or EU agencies.

Developing a multi-step PPA portfolio takes several years.

The buildup of RES capacities, development of storage concepts and transnational energy access (e.g. from the new France-Spain interconnection) is assumed to require at least ten years. This relies strongly on high-level national and EU level policy support for a project of national and international interest.

It is worth highlighting that buildup of energy sources, providing energy and energy storage have a potential to become part of an in-kind contribution strategy for a new Research Infrastructure project, subject to enabling regulatory and technical boundary conditions.

11. EXAMPLES FOR ACTUAL RES INITIATIVES

To provide evidence that the proposed concept is valid, Accenture and McKinsey provided information about currently ongoing similar RES procurement actions carried out by industry key players:

Microsoft and Vattenfall⁵³:

Vattenfall will deliver renewable energy 24/7 to Microsoft's Swedish data centers (Gävle, Sandviken and Staffans-torp) using the 24/7 matching solution to supply electricity via a 10-year PPA that includes measuring the actual consumption in real-time from a **1.3 TWh per year** wind farm.

Vattenfall also delivers EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) labelled hydro and wind power 24/7 to the three data centers in 2021.

With the 24/7 matching solution, Microsoft can track both the data center energy consumption and the renewable energy resource from Vattenfall's wind parks and hydro stations on an hourly basis to ensure matching on-demand 24 hours a day, 365 days a year.

Aes and Google⁵⁴:

On a 10-year contract, AES provides a capacity of **500 MW** renewable energy for Google's Virginia data centers ensuring 90% carbon-free energy.

AES bear the risk of under and over generation by purchasing and selling into the electricity market on an hourly basis as needed, while Google simply pays for their load at a stable \$/MWh.

By combining a diverse set of carbon-free energy resources and a battery that can shift generation hours, AES crafts a portfolio closely tied to Google's load to guarantee that data centers are powered by carbon-free energy 90% of the time.

Engie and Google⁵⁵:

Google has contracted a total capacity of **232 MW** of renewable energy sources from Engie. The deal is **part of a 1.6 GW renewable electricity purchase package with 739 MW contracted in Europe** (92 MW from Belgian offshore wind park in 2019, a 39 MW deal concluded in 2021 to source from German solar PV projects, a 101 MW deal concluded in 2021 for electricity from existing wind parks in Germany). The package makes Google 80% carbon-free by 2022 with a long-term goal to be entirely carbon free by 2030.

TotalEnergies and Orange Telecom in France⁵⁶:

Orange has signed a Corporate PPA with Total to obtain 100 GWh of renewable electricity over a period of 20 years in 2021.

⁵³ <https://group.vattenfall.com/press-and-media/pressreleases/2020/vattenfall-to-deliver-renewable-energy-247-to-microsofts-swedish-datacenters>

⁵⁴ https://www.aes.com/sites/default/files/2021-05/AES-Google-Case-Story_0.pdf

⁵⁵ <https://gems.com/engie-and-google-cloud-join-forces-to-accelerate-wind-energy-development-with-advanced-data-management-and-artificial-intelligence/engie>.

⁵⁶ <https://totalenergies.com/media/news/press-releases/orange-signs-a-major-green-power-purchase-agreement-with-Total>

Orsted, Vattenfall, RWE, Engie and BASF⁵⁷:

BASF's facility in Ludwigshafen (Germany) requires **6 TWh of electricity per year (3 times CERN with the FCC)**. Orsted provides 186 MW from an offshore wind park under a 25-year fixed price corporate PPA. Vattenfall built up 1.5 GW capacities of offshore wind power for 1.6 billion euro becoming operational in 2023 for that contract. RWE develops 2 GW of offshore wind power by 2030 with a dedicated output of 80% to the Ludwigshafen plant. The remaining energy will be used to produce green hydrogen. Engie provides **20.7 TWh of electricity per year from RES** over a time frame of 25 years since January 2022.

⁵⁷ <https://www.basf.com/at/de/who-we-are/sustainability/we-produce-safely-and-efficiently/energy-and-climate-protection/carbon-management/increasing-renewable-energies.html>